

Business and brain: the intersection of ai, creativity and copy right law in India

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Abstract: The biggest Business in the history of human civilization is human brain the creator or originator of all ideas of development/ industrialization/ products and policies too. Since the inception of human race on the planet earth, human beings created several inventions or all unnatural things or products are the creation of human brains, stone arms to fire arms, household utensils to industrial equipment's, telephone to smart watches, computers to super computer, paper to pen, type writers to printing paper and all intelligent inventions to Artificial Intelligence.

Keywords: Business, Brain, Artificial Intelligence, Copyright, Berne Convention, TRIPS & WIPO

“विद्या शस्त्रस्य शास्त्रस्य द्वे विधे प्रतिपत्तेय।

आधा हास्याय वृद्धत्वे द्वितियाद्रियते सदा।।”

“The knowledge and erudition of (Shastra) weapons, weaponry and (Shastra) Vedas, Upanishads, and scriptures are imperative for a decorous life and living. As one ages, the art of weaponry may become laughable as one's body may not support the usage of weapons but wisdom and knowledge of Vedas, Upanishads and scriptures will always be respected.”

The biggest Business in the history of human civilization is human brain the creator or originator of all ideas of development/ industrialization/ products and policies too. Since the inception of human race on the planet earth, human beings created several inventions or all unnatural things or products are the creation of human brains, stone arms to fire arms, household utensils to industrial equipment's, telephone to smart watches, computers to super computer, paper to pen, type writers to printing paper and all intelligent inventions to artificial intelligence. These inventions or ideas are the cause

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Business and Brain: The Intersection of AI, Creativity and Copy Right Law in India

of human civilization vis-a-vis all crimes in the human society, these conflicts are the main cause of chaos in the society, distract a human being from developing idea to destructive ideas or equipment's. All inventions are supposed to perform a idea generated tasks but after certain time new user of all these equipment's or inventions researched/ designed by the human beings like initially stone/ iron/ arms are made for Hunting for survivals used for protection and later on to harm or terrorize the other, like any other invention an important invention in the human civilization was printing press by Johan Gutenberg in 1430's, it was developed form of the olive and wine presses. By 1448 Gutenberg perfected this system. The lead moulds were used for casting the metal types for letters of alphabet. The first book he printed was Bible. Before this Chinese used wood blocks printing in China dates back to 9th century and Korean book makers were printing with moveable metal type a century before². Before the advent of printing press, books were produced as manuscripts, these were hand written books, large produced by scribes, monks and other Dharma Shastri or spiritually enlightened individuals, were valuable passions, made of expensive materials, and individually commissioned by a lord or noble.

In India the first printing press was established at the Jesuit ST. Pauls college in old Goa in 1556. One of the first and the most famous books to be printed on this press was "Catecismo Da Doutrina Crista" this was written by Francis Xavier himself, but it was not printed until five years after his death. Although there is no exact date known between 618-907 CE- the period of the Tang Dynasty the first printing of books started in China. The oldest extent printed book is a work of the "Diamond Sutra" that dates back to 868 CE during the Tang Dynasty³.

The development of printing methodologies printing press becomes the cause of the violation of the identity or right of the author because of easy copying of the work a demand of protection for the author's right is raised in the society.

The world first Copyright Law for the protection of creators was The Statute of Anne Enacted in England in 1710⁴. This Statute introduced the concept of the author of a work being the owner of its Copy Right and laid out fixed terms of protection.

Legislation based on the Statute of Anne⁵ gradually appeared in other countries, such as the Copyright Act. Of 1790 in the United States, but copy right legislation remained uncoordinated at international level until the 19th century. In the year 1886 when the Berne Convention⁶ was introduced to provide mutual recognition of copy right protection at International Plat form with Uniformity⁷.

² Radulescu, R., & Rikhardsdottir, S. (n.d.). *The Routledge Companion to Medieval English Literature*. Taylor & Francis.

³ https://brill.com/display/book/9789004406728/BP000001.xml?language=en&srsIid=AfmBOooMXL08_n09DiXVz4skxV1V_C-ZrX8s92d7VGah2hs4T81brZdM

⁴ https://intellectualpropertyrightsoffice.org/copyright_history/

⁵ . Joyce, Craig, *The Statute of Anne: Yesterday and Today* (December 1, 2010). 47 *Houston Law Review* 779 (2010), U of Houston Law Center No. 2020-A-17, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3627730>

⁶ Solberg, T., Office, L. O. C. C., & O, I. U. F. T. P. (2015). *International Copyright Union: Berne Convention, 1886; Paris Convention, 1896; Berlin Convention, 1908*. Report of the Delegate of the United States to the International Conference for the Revision of the Berne Copyright Convention, Held at Berlin, Germany. Andesite Press.

⁷ 1. Grosse Ruse-Khan H, Metzger A, eds. *The Scope and Mechanisms of International Intellectual Property Treaties*. In: *Intellectual Property Ordering beyond Borders*. Cambridge Intellectual Property and Information Law. Cambridge University Press; 2022:233-308.

This convention does away with the need to register works separately in separate country and has been adopted by almost all the major nations of the world. The Berne Convention remains in force to this day and continues to provide the basis for international copyright law.

Recent technological advancements and development of various new devices and method for effortless or with minimal effort to accomplish any task. In this light the most recent development is artificial intelligence, equipped devices.

“The Day a Computer Writes a Novel” a novel generated by a Japanese AI and a book of Chinese poems “The Sunlight that lost the Glass Window.” Are two notable issues regarding the award of Copy Right to the creation of Artificial Intelligence⁸? At present for the understanding Artificial Intelligence can be sub classified into four parts or four levels.

A. Reactive machine learning:- Reactive machines have not embedded fed memory of the past. Here machine reacts on the information keyed by the user.

When the user of a machine/computer uses it to search for a product/service/information, these preference was stored on the website as well as on the browser. Even when one has closed the website, the pop-up relating to searches has been popping-up through the browser memory and is also popularly known as cookies.

B. Limited Memory Intelligence:- This algorithm or machine learns more with more data. Due to multiple inputs, more images and more information come in the smarter the machine becomes.

C. Theory of Mind:- This is the AI of the future encompassing multiple behavioral intelligence and reactive possibilities that exist not with a person not with an institution but with behavioral patterns of several people and predicting reactions or outcomes of many. In simpler words this kind of AZ gathers data from several heterogeneous sets and predicts the most probable outcome basis on those several sets.

D. Self-Awareness Intelligence:- This is a replica of the human mind, human behavior and human emotions. It has a sense of self awareness, ego, self-assurance, fore sight regarding decision- making, expertise to remove cloudy emotions while articulating the outcome. This kind of AI is yet to come and no tool exists today to have such AI at present.

Indian copy right act, 1957:- The purpose of copyright law in India is to provide a temporary monopoly to the copyright holders to encourage creativity, development of resources and to promote a reward to the creativity creator for the development of art, literature and other heads defined in the protecting law. The question is in which subjects or creation/ideas Copy Right may subsist is answered by the Copy Rights.

Section -13 works in which copyright subsists – (1) Subject to the provisions of this section and the other provisions of this Act, copyright shall subsist throughout India in the following classes of works, that is to say,-

⁸ chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://arxiv.org/pdf/2211.05030

Business and Brain: The Intersection of AI, Creativity and Copy Right Law in India

- (a) Original literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works;
- (b) Cinematograph films; and
- (c) [sound recording]

(2) Copyright shall not subsist in any work specified in sub –section (1), other than a work to which the provisions of section 40 or section 41 apply, unless,-

(i) in the case of a published work, the work is first published in India, or where the work is first published outside India, the author is at the date of such publication, or in a case where the author was dead at that date , was at the time of his death, a citizen of India;

(ii) In the case of an unpublished work other than [work of architecture] the author is at the date making of the work a citizen of India or domiciled in India ; and

(iii) In the case of [work of architecture], the work is located in India.

Explanation- In the case of a work of joint authorship, the conditions conferring copyright specified in this sub-section shall be satisfied by all the authors of the work.

(3) Copyright shall not subsist-

(a) In any cinematograph film if a substantial part of the film is an infringement of the copyright in any other work;

(b) In any [sound recording] made in respect of a literary, dramatic or musical work, if in making the [sound recording], copyright in such work has been infringed.

(4) The copyright in a cinematograph film or a [sound recording] shall not affect the separate copyright in any work in respect of which or a substantial part of which, the film, or as the case may be, the [sound recording] is made.

(5) In the case of [work of architecture], copyright shall subsist only in the artistic character and design and shall not extend to processes or methods of construction⁹.

In the light of above section 13 of Indian Copy Right Act, two view points are came in my thoughts/Brain, one is about the nature of the work i.e. literary, dramatic, musical, artistic, cinematograph films and sound recordings are the subject matters in which the copy right may subsist and another view point is about the citizenship of the author/creator, which is self evident that the law assumed a authorship in the living beings or human beings it may be clearly understandable by the section 2(d) of the same act as:-

Section 2(d) “Author means-

1. In relation to a literary or dramatic work, the author of the work;
2. In relation to a musical work, the composer;
3. In relation to an artistic work other than a photograph, the artist;
4. In relation to a photograph, the person taking the photograph;
5. In relation to a cinematograph film or sound recording, the producer ; and
6. In relation to any literary, dramatic, musical or artistic work which is computer-generated the person who causes the work to be created¹⁰.

When we go through the above subsection the clause 6 of it talks or may try to remove an ambiguity about the authorship, which is a question before us to decide about

⁹ The Copyright Act, 1957 (Act No. 14 of 1957), as amended up to Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012.

¹⁰ The Copyright Act, 1957 (Act No. 14 of 1957), as amended up to Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012.

the copy right ownership, states the in relation to joint venture with computer the authorship will be awarded to the person meaning there by a living being and sub section 2(O) defines literary work as:-

Section 2(O) “Literary work” includes computer programs, tables and compilations including computer [databases]¹¹

For understanding and clarification for the authorship/ownership we need to analyse the section 17, 22 and 54 of Indian Copy Right Law. These provisions are capable to explain the subject matter of substance and to whom law may provide the authorship/CRD time frame for the same and also about the ownership of the Copy Right assignment too. The law for the same as reproduced

Section 17- First owner of copyright- Subject to the provisions of this act, the author of a work shall be the first owner of the copyright therein.

Provided that-

- (a) In the case of a literary, dramatic or artistic work made by the author in the course of his employment by the proprietor of a newspaper, magazine or similar periodical under a contract of service or apprenticeship, for the purpose of publication in a newspaper, magazine or similar periodical, the said proprietor shall, in the absence of any agreement to the contrary, be the first owner of all copyright in the work in any newspaper, magazine or similar periodical, or to the reproduction of the work purpose of its being so published, but in all other respects the author shall be the first owner of the copyright in the work;
- (b) Subject to the provisions of clause (a), in the case of a photograph taken, or a painting or portrait drawn, or an engraving or a cinematograph film made, for valuable consideration at the instance of any person, such person shall, in the absence of any agreement to contrary, be the first owner of the copyright therein;
- (c) In the case of a work made in the course of the author’s employment under the contract of service or apprenticeship, to which clause (a) or clause (b) does not apply, the employer shall, in the absence of any agreement to the contrary, be the first owner of the copyright therein;

[(cc) In the case of any address or speech delivered in public, the person who has delivered, such address or speech or if such person has delivered such address or speech on behalf of any other person, such other person shall be the first owner of the copyright therein notwithstanding that the person who delivers such address or speech, or, as the case may be, the person on whose behalf such address or speech in delivered, is employed by any other person who arranges such address or speech or on whose behalf or premises such address or speech is delivered;]

- (d) In the case of a Government work, Government shall, in the absence of any agreement to the contrary, be the first owner of the copyright therein;

[(dd) In the case of a work made or first published by or under the direction or control of any public undertaking, such public undertaking shall, in the absence of any agreement to the contrary, be the first owner of the copyright therein.

¹¹ The Copyright Act, 1957 (Act No. 14 of 1957), as amended up to Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012.

Business and Brain: The Intersection of AI, Creativity and Copy Right Law in India

Explanation- For the purposes of this clause and section 28A,” public undertaking” means-

1. An undertaking owned or controlled by Government; an
 2. A Government company as defined in section 617 of the companies act, 1956 (1 of 1956) ; or
 3. A body corporate established by or under any central, provincial or state act;]
- (e) In the case of a work to which the provisions of section 41 apply, the international organization concerned shall be the first owner of the copyright therein.

Section 22- Term of copyright in published literary, dramatic, musical and artistic works- Except as otherwise hereinafter provided, copyright shall subsist in any literary, dramatic, musical or artistic work (other than a photograph) published within the lifetime of the author until (sixty years) from the beginning of the calendar year next following the year in which the author dies.

Explanation- In this section the reference to the author shall, in the case of a work of joint authorship, be construed as a reference to the author who dies last¹².

Section 54 – Definition- For the purpose of this chapter, unless the context otherwise requires, the expression “owner of copyright” shall include-

- (a) An exclusive licensee;
- (b) In the case of an anonymous or pseudonymous literary, dramatic, musical or artistic work, the publisher of the work, until the identity of the author or, in the case of an anonymous work of joint authorship, or a work of joint authorship published under names all of which are pseudonyms, the identity of any of the authors, is disclosed publicly by the author and the publisher or is otherwise established to the satisfaction of the copyright board by that author or his legal representatives¹³.

Going through the above mentioned provisions it becomes very clear that only living beings were the creator/Author/ of Subject matter comes under the Indian Copy Right law.

International Treaties and Conventions:-

Indian copyright law is at parity with the international standards as contained in TRIPS. The (Indian) Copyright Act, 1957, pursuant to the amendments in 1999, 2002, and 2012, fully reflects the Berne Convention for Protection of Literary and Artistic Works, 1886, and the Universal Copyrights Convention, to which India is a party, India is also a party to the Geneva Convention for the Protection of Rights of Producers of Phonograms and is an active member of the world Intellectual Property Organization

¹² The Copyright Act, 1957 (Act No. 14 of 1957), as amended up to Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012.

¹³ The Copyright Act, 1957 (Act No. 14 of 1957), as amended up to Copyright (Amendment) Act, 2012.

(WIPO) and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)¹⁴.

Judicial Response:

The United States Supreme Court held in *Feist Publications Inc. V. Rural Telephone Service Co. Inc.*¹⁵ that the sine qua non of copyright is originality. To qualify for copyright protection, a work must be original to the author. Original means only that the work was independently created by the author, and that it possesses at least some minimal level of creativity. To look at the example of the Next Rembrandt- a new artwork, that was made by the computer by an analysis of thousands of works of the 17th-century Dutch artist Rembrandt Harmenszoon van Rijn¹⁶, manifests that AI is capable of creating original art forms, thereby satisfying the criteria of originality i.e., one of the essentials of copyright.

The standard of the modicum of creativity was laid down in the case of *Eastern Book Company v. D.B. Modak*¹⁷. In this case, the Supreme Court held that for establishing copyright, the application of creativity standard does not mean that something must be novel or non-obvious, but some amount of creativity in the work to claim copyright was required. It did require a minimal degree of creativity¹⁸. The landmark case of the U.S. Supreme Court, *Feist Publications Inc. v. Rural Telephone Service Co. Inc* held that “the requisite level of creativity is extremely low; even a slight amount will suffice.¹⁹” An interesting example of AI depicting creativity is ‘Jukedek’ that “produces unique music for commercial use in seconds; the user only needs to specify the genre, the mood, and the length of the song, and the site’s neural network will produce a royalty-free composition that can be incorporated into a video or any other derivative work²⁰. In *R.G Anand v. M/S Delux Films*²¹, it was held that the law does not recognize property rights in abstract ideas, nor is an idea protected by copyright, it becomes copyright and subsists only when the idea is given embodiment in a tangible form. The case of *Tata Consultancy Services v. State of Andhra Pradesh*²² held the computer programs to be tangible. If computer programs are held to be tangible, so should be the works autonomously produced by AI be treated as fixed in a tangible form.

¹⁴ <https://www.studocu.com/in/document/maharaja-agrasen-international-college/introduction-to-microeconomics/copyright-overview-international-treaties-indian-copyright-law/120562611>

¹⁵ *Feist Publication Inc v. Rural Telephone Services Co. Inc.*, 499US340

¹⁶ The GUARDIAN, <https://www.theguardian.com/artanddesign/2016/apr/05/new-rembrandt-to-be-unveiled-in-amsterdam> visited 29, June 2021

¹⁷ *Eastern Book Company V.D.B. Modak* (2008) SCC

¹⁸ *Syndicate of the Press of the University of Cambridge V.B.D. Bhandari*

¹⁹ *Feist Publication Inc v. Rural Telephone Services Co. Inc.*, 499US340

²⁰ Andres Guadamus, Do androids dream of electric copyright, comparative analysis of originality in artificial intelligence generated works, Sussex Research online (June 29, 2021, 3:45PM)

²¹ *R.G. Anand Vs. M/s Delux Films*, AIR 1978 SC 1613

²² *Tata Consultancy Services V. State of Andhra Pradesh* (2004) 137STC620

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